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Deliverable D3.1

Standard operating procedures for sampling, isolation, and preservation

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
ABS	Access and Benefit Sharing
BSS	Bulk Soil Sample
CG	Climate Change
CLC	Corine Land Cover
DMP	Data Management Plan
GPS	Global Positioning System
RSS	Rhizospheric Soil Sample
RES	Root Endospheric sample
SMC	Synthetic Microbial Community
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure

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About the project

Terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems are being challenged by global changes, with threats to agricultural and forestry ecosystems representing some of the most serious environmental and socio-economic menaces that the planet and humanity are currently facing. Climate change (CG) is widely recognized as one of the most impactful global changes, and since it goes hand-by-hand with biodiversity and services loss in terrestrial ecosystems, they should be tackled together. Microbes constitute the life support system of the biosphere, but they are its most overlooked fraction and are not considered in the context of CG. The overall understanding of the impact of CG on the assembly and functions of microbiomes is still very limited. How the complex microbe-plant-soil interactions and its consequences on plant performance and productivity are impacted by CG is still largely unknown. Additional knowledge also needs to be obtained on the overall ecosystem functioning, and to what extent microbiomes may mitigate stress conditions due to CG. The project MICROBES-4-CLIMATE will provide a wider community of users/researchers, irrespective of location, with efficient access to a cluster of complementary world-class Research Infrastructures and their integrated, advanced services along with training and scientific and/or technical support, to address such needs. An excellence-driven program of Transnational Access, which is at the core of the project, will enable users to conduct curiosity-driven research addressing terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems, in light of the above mentioned multidimensional and still poorly understood microbiome-plant-soil environment interactions, and its roles in CG responses, resilience, and mitigation. This will foster the advancement of frontier knowledge and also pave the way towards applied research on harnessing plant-microbiome interactions to improve the climate resiliency of plants/crops and to enable e.g., precision, sustainable and resilient agriculture.

Executive Summary

Work package WP3 – Establishment and validation of synthetic microbial communities

The overall objective of WP3 is to set up a workflow for establishing synthetic microbial communities (SMCs) to support vulnerable terrestrial systems (e.g., forests, agriculture, urban sites), which are likely to be severely affected by climate change, particularly by drought and temperature rise. WP3 aims to: establish standardized procedures for reproducible sampling (including metadata collection), processing, and preservation of soil and plant samples; isolate, characterize, and preserve novel bacterial and fungal isolates from soil and plant microbiomes; collect information on microbiome diversity and their functional potential; establish and validate synthetic microbial communities (SMCs) comprising key taxa in the investigated ecosystems. These resources will be preserved and made available for future research and applications. Furthermore, a comprehensive workflow will be developed to enable the development of SMCs for other environments/research questions. The specific objectives of WP3 are: To establish a sampling strategy for the collection of new, valuable microbial resources from vulnerable and stressed habitats (Task 3.1); To isolate and taxonomically characterize new microorganisms (focusing on bacteria and fungi) (Task 3.2); to perform microbiome, genome, and advanced bioinformatic analyses to select key taxa in vulnerable and stressed habitats, and to establish and preserve SMCs displaying key ecosystem functions (Task 3.3); To test selected SMCs for their protective effects on plants against abiotic stress typically induced by climate change (e.g. drought, high temperatures) (Task 3.4).

1. Introduction

Our specific goals in this document are to define: i) the required metadata associated with wheat field sites to be sampled in three countries to study microbial communities associated with water stress, ii) the common sampling strategies for bulk soils, rhizosphere and root endosphere investigation, and iii) the protocols to isolate and molecularly characterize microorganisms (bacteria and fungi)

It is crucial that experimental protocols are as harmonized as possible between partners working on different sites in different countries, to enable optimum comparative analysis and minimize confusing effects.

D3.1 – Standard operating procedures for sampling, isolation, and preservation

The aim is to describe the experimental set-up common to the members of the MICROBES-4-CLIMATE consortium involved in WP3, in accordance with the recommendations established in other communities, to ensure optimum standardization of procedures. During the project, we will focus on the microbial communities associated with bulk soil, rhizosphere soil and root endosphere samples collected from wheat fields faced with different levels of water stress in three countries: France, Italy and Greece.

2. Procedures

2.1 Choice of sampling sites and Associated metadata

In the frame of the MICROBES-4-CLIMATE project, we aim to collect samples from 5 sampling sites in three countries (France, Greece and Italy). The final choice of sites will be made at the beginning of 2025 in order to select contrasting sites across the three countries on the basis of pedoclimatic conditions and drought stress. The general workflow is presented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: General overview of the sampling strategy and isolation.

Logistical aspect

As the project aims to isolate viable bacteria and fungi, we need to evaluate the travel time between the region of sampling and the location of the laboratory/institute to reduce the adverse effects on the viability of microorganisms as well as the costs and CO₂ emission.

Table 1: List of mandatory and additional required metadata to define each sampling site.

		Mandatory	DATA	COMMENTS
	Plot name/ID	X		
Location data	Latitude	X		
Location data	Longitude	X		
Climatic data	Temperatures records	X		
Climatic data	Wind records			
Climatic data	Rainfall records	X		
Pedologic data	Pedology - Soil classification ¹			
Pedologic data	Pedology - Soil texture ²	X		
Pedologic data	Sand, Silt, Clay (%)	X		
Pedologic data	pH	X		
Pedologic data	Total Carbon			
Pedologic data	Soil Organic Carbon			
Pedologic data	Water content	X		
Pedologic data	Phosphorus			
Pedologic data	Nitrogen			
Ecological data	CLC nomenclature ³			
Ecological data	Irrigation regime			
Ecological data	Fertilization regime			
Ecological data	Mowed			
Ecological data	Tillaged			
Ecological data	Pesticide use			
Ecological data	Crop rotation			
Ecological data	Dominant plant species			
Ecological data	Visual plant cover			
	Picture			
Ecological data	Crop variety			
Ecological data	Crop detail (phenology)			
	Wheat yield			

¹. IUSS Working Group WRB. 2022. World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria.

https://wrb.isric.org/files/WRB_fourth_edition_2022-12-18.pdf

². texture triangle (USDA, 2017) available in Annexe 6.1

³. <https://land.copernicus.eu/content/corine-land-cover-nomenclature-guidelines/html/index.html>

2.2 Sampling and processing protocols for bulk soil, rhizosphere soil and root endosphere

2.2.1 Goal

Sampling of bulk soil, rhizosphere and root endosphere.

2.2.2 Scope

This procedure describes the procedures for the sampling of bulk soil, rhizospheric soil and root endosphere. Our definition of rhizospheric soil is the soil that remains attached to the thin root layer after vigorous shaking.

2.2.3 Plot and sample selection

The selected plot must have a minimal dimension of a square of 30x30 m

The plot must be georeferenced. A rapid GPS survey of the selected area will be used to return to the site for installation. It is not necessary to perform a precise GPS location as described in the RMQS2 manual (https://www.gissol.fr/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Manuel_V_Num2.pdf).

Important: Make a screenshot of the plot with a geolocation app (type strava or Google Earth). The picture should be deposited in a defined folder in the collaborative space (defined in the DMP).

Selection of 5 randomly healthy chosen plants at similar phenological state.

Important: Make pictures of the sampled plants (whole plant, root and leaves)

The picture should be deposited in S3 archive or in a defined folder in the collaborative space (defined in the DMP).

Naming of the samples

To harmonize the naming and facilitate the subsequent analysis, we proposed the following rules for the naming. Samples have to be identified with the following parameters:

Year_month (3 letters)_day_ plotNameID_number of the sampled plant (1 to 5)_nature of the sample (BSS: Bulk Soil Sample, RES: Root Endospheric sample, RSS: rhizospheric soil sample_DNA (for gDNA extraction) or CULT (for cultivation of microorganisms)

Example: 2024_Oct_1_Javron_1_BSS_DNA⇒ Bulk soil sample from plant 1 collected at Javron site on October 1st, 2024 intended for DNA extraction

2.2.4 Sampling and sample preparation

The equipment enables samples to be taken, transferred in storage containers and stored at 4°C while minimizing contamination (see Annex 8.1).

To prevent contamination, change the gloves between each sample collection. Wear gloves always sterilized with EtOH. Sterilize all equipment with 70% EtOH and wipe between samples.

The sampling protocols for BSS, RES, RSS were derived from the ones described in the document entitled “SOPs for sampling of microbiome in different ecosystems” (<https://zenodo.org/records/10887823>) developed in the frame of the [SUS.MIRRI.IT](https://www.sus-mirri.it) project. The proposed protocols aim to isolate non symbiotic microorganisms (nitrogen fixing bacteria or arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi). A specific protocole sampling of AMF isolation is described in Annex 6.5.

Figure 2: General overview of sampling and sample preparation.

2.2.5 Bulk Soil Sample (BSS) collection

2.2.5.1 Field work

1. Sterilize soil core sampler with 70% EtOH between each biological replicate and wipe it clean.
2. Use a soil core sampler with adequate diameter and extension based on the plant's dimensions.
3. Collect 5 soil cores (0-20 cm horizon) in a radial pattern (more than 20 cm) for each biological replicate.

4. Pour the collected soil into a bucket and thoroughly mix to produce a composite soil for each biological replicate.
5. Remove vegetation residues, grass and litter, if present, from the surface before sampling and from the composite sample.
6. Sieve the bulk-soil at **4-mm** and split the soils in **two** batches (minimal weight 100 g), transfer into zipped plastic bag properly labelled as indicated (**2.2.3**). All samples will be stored on ice during field work.
7. Transfer to the laboratory on ice (0-4°C, e.g., thermo-stable shipping box) **within 24h**. Samples must be processed immediately on arrival at the laboratory.

2.2.5.2 Laboratory work

8. Once received, immediately transfer a minimum of 20 g BSS from the labelled DNA bags in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube numbered 1 and 2 and store at **-20°C** until DNA extraction. Repeat this step for each biological replicate.
9. For the CULT bags, transfer BSS in in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube numbered 1 and 2 weigh and store at 4°C. The viability of bacteria and fungi could be harmed during long period at 4°C and selection biases could occur in favor to microorganisms that can enter in stasis (spore development). **For BSS**, we are recommending that isolation of microorganisms has to be performed in less **that one month** after the receipt of the soils. **For RES**, as the root tissues could be deteriorated, we are recommending that isolation of microorganisms has to be performed in less that **one week** after the receipt of the root tissues.

Important: As we may experience problems during the shipment that could result in the alteration (e.g., by thawing) or loss of samples, it is essential to prepare at least two aliquots for each use. The DNA aliquot numbered 1 will be sent to AIT for the gDNA extraction. The CULT aliquot numbered 1 will be used for the isolation of microorganisms, which will be carried out in each partner laboratories that carried out the sampling (INRAE, UNITO, NKUA). The DNA and CULT aliquots numbered 2 will be kept as a backup (for the storage conditions see Section 2.3).

2.2.6 Rhizospheric Soil Sample (RSS) collection

2.2.6.1 Field work

1. Sterilize two scalpels with 70% EtOH between each biological replicate and wipe them clean.
2. Dig with the shovel within a 10 cm radius around the plant and down to 20 cm soil depth to remove the entire root system.
3. Shake the roots vigorously to remove the large soil aggregates OR.

Manually remove excessive non-adhering soil by vigorous shaking and using a scalpel or pot spade.

6. Collect soil detached from different areas of the plant root system, split into **two** batches (approximately 20 g each) and transfer into zipped plastic bag properly labelled as indicated (**2.2.3**). All samples should be kept on ice during field work.
7. Keep the root system for the next step (see 3.2.7).
8. Transfer to the laboratory on ice (0-4°C, e.g., thermo-stable shipping box) **within 24h**. Samples must be processed immediately on arrival at the laboratory.

2.2.6.2 Laboratory work

9. Once received process the samples within 24h
10. Transfer a minimum of 5 g collected RSS from the labelled DNA bags in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube numbered 1 and 2 and store at **-20°C** until DNA extraction. Repeat this step for each biological replicate.
11. For the CULT bags, transfer a minimum of 5 g RSS in in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube numbered 1 and 2 weigh and store them in accordance with point **2.3.3**.

2.2.7 Root Endospheric Sample (RES) collection

Figure 3: Wheat root system.

2.2.7.1 Field work

1. Transfer the roots after retrieving of the rhizospheric soil (step 7 in 2.2.6.1) into individual labelled zipped plastic bags and store in ice during field work.
2. Preserved samples collected in ice (0-4°C) and transfer to the laboratory within 24h

2.2.7.2 Laboratory work

3. Once received, dissect the root system **within 24h** after reception.
4. Select primary or secondary lateral roots. Sample lateral roots and cut them in 3 cm root segments with a sterile scalpel (Fig. 3).
5. Transfer root segments for “DNA extraction – ENDOSPHERE” in two 50 mL centrifuge tubes (numbered 1 and 2) containing a minimum of 1 g per aliquot and store at -20°C . Repeat this step for each biological replicate.
Transfer root segments for “FOR MICROORGANISMS ISOLATION – ENDOSPHERE” in two aliquots (50 mL centrifuge tube numbered 1 and 2), and store at 4°C.
6. Transfer a minimum of 1 g collected RES in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube labelled DNA 1 and DNA 2 and store at -20°C until DNA extraction. Repeat this step for each biological replicate.
7. Transfer a minimum of 10 g (if possible) collected RES in in two sterile 50 mL centrifuge tube labelled CULT 1 and CULT 2, weigh and store them in accordance with point **2.3.3**.

2.3 Conservation and shipping of the bulk soil, rhizosphere and root samples

2.3.1 Samples for metabarcoding sequencing

Shipping to AIT is made on dry ice.

The batch of samples has to be sent to the following address:

Tanja Kostic / Cintia Mayr
 AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
 Konrad Lorenz Strasse 24
 3430 Tulln
 Austria

2.3.2 Samples for Culturomics

Isolation of the microorganisms should be started as soon as possible.

2.3.3 Conservation of microbial consortia in glycerol stock

For the backup sample for microorganisms isolation, a mid- to long-term preservation strategy will be devised. The current state of the art is to store samples at 4°C. However, this might not be optimal as it could lead to rotting or mould development on the moistened samples. Air drying could be considered for long-term storage but could introduce a bias in the composition of microbial communities. Glycerol stocks (final concentration glycerol 15%) could also be considered, in particular for BSS (3.2.5.2) or RSS (3.2.6.2) samples.

The EU project MICROBE (<https://www.microbeproject.eu/>) is currently evaluating 16 different cryopreservation approaches for the soil microbiomes. Preservation efficiency is being evaluated three months post-preservation, and the results are expected in Q4/2024. Based on the outcomes of this work an improved strategy might be devised and recommended for use. In this case this Deliverable document will be updated accordingly.

2.4 Isolation and characterization (incl. dereplication) of microorganisms from bulk soil, rhizosphere and endosphere

2.4.1 Materials and Equipment

The equipment (listed in Annex 6.2) enables the isolation of microorganisms from bulk soil, rhizosphere and root endosphere samples.

2.4.2 Isolation of Bacteria

2.4.2.1 Goal

The isolation of bacteria from bulk soil, rhizosphere and root endosphere samples.

2.4.2.2 Scope

This procedure is designed to isolate bacteria from soil, rhizosphere and root endosphere. Diluted bulk soil sample, rhizospheric soil or pulverized and surface disinfected root are streaked out on Petri dishes containing medium and then incubated. Colonies are picked out, recultured and preserved as glycerol stocks. This method yields axenic strains of soil bacteria and endobacteria.

We plan to keep around 30 bacterial clones per sample (selected on the basis of colony morphology, etc). This will give us a total of 6750 isolates (3 countries x 5 sampling sites x 3 compartments) for the dereplication stage.

2.4.2.3 Media, solutions and reagents

The composition and recipes for different media equipment are listed in Annex 6.3.

Table 2: List of media used for bacterial isolation

	<i>Used in paragraph</i>
Nutrient Agar (NA)	6
10% Tryptic Soy Agar (10% TSA)	6
Arginine Glycerol Salt (AGS) Agar	6
70% ethanol for surface disinfection	5
0.9 % NaCl solution	4,5
Optional: Stock solution of cycloheximide (100g/L)	6

2.4.2.4 Samples preparation for isolation from BSS or RSS

1. 1 g of soil is added to 10 ml of a sterile 0.9 % NaCl solution.
2. The soil suspensions are then incubated to homogenize bacterial content on an orbital shaker (300 rpm, 90 min, temperature at 25 °C) and then centrifuged (150 g, Eppendorf 5810-R, 25 °C, 10 min) in sterile tubes to concentrate the soil particles in the pellet.
3. The supernatant is filtered using 1 mm sieves to eliminate remaining soil residues.
4. Ten-fold serial dilutions are prepared in a sterile NaCl 0.9 % solution (1 ml + 9 ml) until reaching 10^{-8} dilution.

2.4.2.5 Samples preparation for isolation from RES

The following protocol is a modified version of the one described in 3.5.2.4:

1. Root samples (3 cm segments) are washed with tap water to remove any soil remnants.
2. Surface sterilization is performed in 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) for 5 min followed by three times (30 s) rinsing in sterile water. Subsequently, root fragments are surface-disinfected in 70% EtOH for 1 min and rinsed three times (30 s) in sterile water.
3. 100 μ l of the final sterile water wash were plated on NA to check for bacterial contamination by non-endophytic bacteria.
4. The surface disinfected root samples are ground with a mortar and pestle and 1.5 g of root sample are transferred to sterile 15 ml Falcon tubes containing 3 ml of sterile NaCl 0.9 % solution.
5. Ten-fold serial dilutions are prepared in a sterile NaCl 0.9 % solution (1 ml + 9 ml) until reaching 10^{-3} dilution.

2.4.2.6 Plating and clone isolation

The plating will be optimized as far as possible by adjusting dilution so that the colonie number per plate will be in the 30-100 range as morphology and phenotype could be hard to distinguish with high density plating.

100 μ l of each dilution are spread in triplicate on 90 mm Petri-dishes containing NA, 10% TSA or AGS Agar.

Optional: Medium can be supplemented with 100 mg/l cycloheximide to act as an antifungal or with 100 mg/l potassium dichromate to inhibit fungi and fast-growing bacteria.

The NA plates are incubated at 25-30°C for 3 days and the 10% TSA and AGS plates are incubated for 5 days at 28°C.

Individual colonies with different phenotypes (maximum 10 per media) are randomly picked with a pipette tip and streaked out on a fresh Petri dish containing the same medium as previously used.

Axenic cultures are suspended in 15% Glycerol solution and stored at -80 °C.

2.4.3 Isolation of Fungi

2.4.3.1 Goal

The isolation of fungi from bulk soil, rhizosphere and root endosphere samples.

2.4.3.2 Scope

This procedure is designed to isolate saprotrophic fungi from soil, rhizosphere and the root endosphere. Diluted soil sample or sterilized root sample are streaked out on Petri dishes containing agar and then incubated. Colonies are picked out, recultured and preserved as glycerol stocks. This method yields axenic fungal strains.

We target to have an initial collection of 10 fungal clones per sample (2 isolates per media). We expect to have a total of 225 samples (3 countries x 5 sampling sites x 3 compartments), so a maximum of 2250 isolates prior to dereplication.

2.4.3.3 Growth media and solutions

The composition and recipes for different media equipment are listed in Annex 6.3.

Table 3: List of media used for isolation of fungi

	Used in paragraph
Phosphate Buffer Saline-Tween (PBS-T) (10 mM, pH 7.4)	4
Physiological solution (NaCl 0.9%)	4
Hypochlorite Sodium 4% (v/v)	5
Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)	4, 5
Malt Extract Agar (MEA)	4
Corn Meal Agar (CMA)	4
Czapek Dox Agar (CDA)	4
Soil Extract Agar Medium (SEA)	4

2.4.3.4 Isolation of saprotrophic fungi from bulk soil and rhizospheric soil by dilution

1. Resuspend 1 g of bulk soil or rhizospheric soil in 20 ml 10mM Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS-T) pH 7.4. Shake on a rocker for 15-20 minutes at 120/180 rpm;
2. Vortex for 30 seconds and sonicate for 1 minute (150/160W);
3. Vortex for 30 seconds and perform 5 cycles of sonication for 30 seconds each, with 30-second intervals between each sonication (150/160W);
4. Centrifuge for 20 minutes at a minimum of 5000 rpm. Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 10 ml of 10 mM PBS-T buffer;

5. The supernatant is filtered using 1 mm sieves to eliminate remaining soil residues.
6. Prepare ten-fold serial dilutions in sterile physiological solution (NaCl 0.9%) up to 10^{-6} ;
7. Plate 100 μ l aliquots of the diluted soil suspensions on five rich media agar-enriched media (PDA/MEA/CMA/CDA/SEA) supplemented with antibiotic (50 mg/L of chloramphenicol);
8. Incubate at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 days;
9. Isolate 2 individual single clones per media (if possible) with a sterile tip and transfer them onto PDA/MEA/CMA/CDA/SEA plates.

2.4.3.5 Isolation of root endophytic fungi

1. For the isolation of root endophytic fungi, washed root segments thoroughly with tap water;
2. Cut the segments into small tissue segments about $5 \times 5 \times 5$ mm;
3. Select randomly ten tissue segments and surface sterilize by consecutive immersions for 30 s in 70% ethanol, 2 min in 4% sodium hypochlorite and finally rinse three times with sterile water;
4. The efficacy of the sterilization procedure to remove surface fungi is tested by making the imprints of the surface sterilized segments on PDA plates and smearing 0.2 ml of the last rinse water onto PDA plates.
5. The sterilized tissue segments are placed onto PDA/MEA/CMA/CDA/SEA with five segments per plate and incubated at 28°C for 5 days;
6. Isolate two individual single colonies of fungal mycelium with a sterile tip and transfer them onto PDA/MEA/CMA/CDA/SEA plates.

2.4.4 taxonomic assignment of isolated clones

2.4.4.1 Goal

Taxonomical assignment of isolated strain

2.4.4.2 Scope

The global purpose is to allow the identification of isolated strains at a taxonomical level that allow the dereplication of the strain collection.

2.4.4.3 Solutions and reagents

Extraction buffer for bacteria

10 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6

50 mM KCl

0.1 % Tween 20

2.4.4.4 Primers for taxonomical assignment

Bacteria : V5-V7 799f (5'-AACMGGATTAGATACCCKG-3') and 1175r (5'-ACGTCRTCCCCDCCTTCCT-3') Bonder et al, 2012, Mitter et al, 2017

Fungi : ITS1F (5'-CTTGGTCATTTAGAGGAAGTAA-3') and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3')

The selected primers do not allow a species-level identification. The aim of this step is to enable the dereplication of isolates. If a species level identification is needed and depending on the taxonomic position identified with the above-listed primers, different primer pairs, and/or a combination of them could be used. Where possible, MALDI TOF will be used for taxa that are well represented in the databases (this also applies to bacteria).

2.4.4.5 Bacteria fast DNA extraction (only for DNA identification by 16S sequencing)

Single colonies are resuspended in 50 µl sterile water (approximate concentration of 10⁵ cfu/ml)

0,5 µl of bacterial suspension is mixed with 4,5 µl extraction buffer (2.5.4.3)

The mixture is heated at 100°C in thermocycler for 10 min and immediately placed on ice

After centrifugation at 6000 g for 5 min, 1 µl of the supernatant is used for the PCR.

2.4.4.6 Fungal DNA extraction

As fungal diversity is high, there is no “one fits all” solution for fungal DNA extraction. In the majority of the cases, the commercial kits designed for DNA extraction from plants (e.g. the DNeasy series from QIAGEN and the Macherey-Nagel NucleoSpin) can be used. In the case of recalcitrant isolates a classical phenol/chloroform-based extraction could be done (<https://www.mycologylab.org/images/methodsProtocols/FungalDNAExtraction.pdf>).

2.4.4.7 PCR conditions

25 µl reaction volume containing 200 nM of each primer, 300 µM dNTPs, 0.5 units HiFidelity DNA Polymerase (e.g., KAPA HiFi from Kapa Biosystems or Phusion), 1x buffer, 1 µl of bacterial suspension or 5 ng fungal gDNA as a template. The amplification conditions are as follows: initial denaturation for 5 min at 95°C, 25x 30 s at 95°C, 30 s at annealing temperature (bacteria 55°C; fungi 52°C) and 30 s at 72°C, and a final elongation for 5 min at 72°C. The amplified section will be sequenced by one extremity (799F or ITS4) to decrease the cost of sequencing. Sequencing will be organised by partners that isolated microorganisms using Sanger technology.

2.4.4.8 Bioinformatics analysis

Step 1: Taxonomical assignment

The sequence will be analyzed by identity analysis against public nt database: SILVA (for bacteria) / UNITE (for Fungi).

The following websites has to be used :

SILVA <https://www.arb-silva.de/aligner/>

Select the “Search and classify” box with the following parameters

Figure 4: Selected parameters for search for SILVA database.

UNITE (<https://unite.ut.ee/analysis.php>)

Figure 5: Selected parameters for fungi identification.

A minimal threshold of 99% identity could be used to assign the strain at the genus level the isolated strains. If the sequence displays less than 95% of identity with available sequences in the respective database, these strains could be classified at a higher taxa.

Step 2: Phylogenetic analysis for selection of clones

However, microbial strains with identical taxon level could present a nucleotide polymorphism. An alignment will be carried out using Mega10 (<https://www.megasoftware.net/>) with the Muscle algorithm (Edgard, 2021) or clustalx (Larkin et al, 2007) on a dataset corresponding to all the sequences obtained from the three partners.

A total of 100 isolated strains (60 bacterial and 40 fungi) will be selected to maximise geographic, taxonomic diversity and climatic conditions. These strains will be fully sequenced (Illumina + nanopore) and annotated.

3. Legal and Ethical Issues

Before embarking on an isolation campaign, a number of legal and ethical issues need to be considered.

With regard to the legal aspects, the procedure and type of agreements required between project partners may vary considerably depending on the purpose of the project, the type of genetic resources (GR) targeted and the location of the sampling areas. These agreements should be set up during the preparatory phase of the project.

Soil sampling for microbes should address biosafety management, access and benefit-sharing (ABS), and intellectual property rights.

3.1 Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS)

The implementation of the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing (ABS) imposes different constraints on sampling, depending on the national regulations adopted in different countries. Consequently, the organization of this field sampling has to be determined in accordance with the ABS rules implemented in Greece, Italy and France, where the field sampling will take place. Recently, the ABS rules for France have been modified as cultivated microorganisms isolated from the soil are considered domesticated and no longer require Prior Informed Consent (PIC) and Mutually Agreed Terms (MAT) for the main French inland areas. In Greece and Italy there are no specific procedures to follow.

However, the agreement of the owner of the field to be studied should be obtained before the sampling.

3.2 Biosafety and biosecurity compliance

The laboratory involved in the soil sampling project should assess appropriate biosafety and biosecurity compliance. As this project does not aim to isolate pathogenic or toxin-producing microorganisms, the partners do not require an agreement before collecting or processing the natural samples. However, during the isolation and characterization phases, microorganisms with biosafety constraints may be encountered, such as *Cryptococcus gattii*, which is classified as BSL2 class fungus. Other BSL2 or BSL3 microorganisms may be isolated (<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1833/2020-06-24>, microorganisms on the quarantine list (<http://www.eppo.int/QUARANTINE/quarantine.htm>), on the dual-use list (<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/821/oj>). If so, further manipulation of these microorganisms should be carried out in a laboratory approved for the manipulation of these microorganisms.

3.3 Intellectual property

Intellectual property of microorganisms should be defined as early as possible. A prior agreement with the field owner about the property of the microorganisms should be made to ensure future use of these resources. This is indeed essential if these resources are possibly offered to a wide community freely.

3.4 Intervention in European protected sites

In the case of European protected sites, legal requirements for entry into the site, sampling and all actions for the preservation of the biodiversity and integrity of the site must be fulfilled. Visualization of the protected sites across Europe is available here: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/explore-interactive-maps/european-protected-areas-1>.

4. Conclusions

This SOP was developed based on the current state of the art and considering practical experience of the involved partners. If necessary, based on new insights from the project MICROBE or scientific literature, this document will be revised and updated before the sampling starts in spring 2025.

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6. Annex

6.1 Soil texture triangle

Figure 6: Texture triangle (USDA, 2017).

Adapted from Moreno-Maroto et al. 2022

6.2 Sampling and shipment equipment

- Gloves
- 70% EtOH
- Shovel
- Scissors or shears
- Pots spades
- Scalpels
- Sieve (4mm) (we prefer to sieve at 4mm because it's easier to sieve soils with high proportion of clay)
- Soil coring equipment
- Zipped plastic bags
- Permanent markers
- 50mL and 15mL centrifuge tubes
- Thermostable shipping box
- Buckets
- Ice packs
- kitchen scale

6.3 Needed equipment for isolation of microorganisms

- Laminar flow hood
- Autoclave
- Incubator
- Sterile pipettes
- Sterile Petri dishes
- Permanent pens
- Spatula
- Bunsen burner
- Scale
- Falcon tubes
- Eppendorf tubes
- Vortex
- Mechanical shaker
- Mortar and pestle
- 1 mm sieves

6.4 Media recipes

Bacteria : Nutrient Agar (NA) General purpose medium that supports the growth of a wide range of microorganisms.

Beef extract	1 g/L
peptone	5 g/L
sodium chloride	5 g/L
yeast extract	2 g/L
agar	15 g/L

Bacteria : 10% Tryptic Soy Agar (10% TSA) organisms. Nutrient poor medium for isolation of bacteria.

Casein peptone (pancreatic)	1.7 g/L
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.25 g/L
glucose	0.25 g/L
NaCl	0.5 g/L
soya peptone (papain digest)	0.3 g/L
agar	15 g/L

Bacteria : Arginine Glycerol Salt (AGS) Agar Nutrient poor medium designed to isolate actinobacteria or other relatively slow-growing bacteria.

Glycerol	12.5 g/L
L-arginine hydrochloride	1.2 g/L
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	1.3 g/L
NaCl	1.0 g/L
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.5 g/L
Agar	15.0 g/L
Metal trace solution	1ml/1L

Metal trace solution

Fe₂(SO₄)₃ 10 g/L, CuSO₄ 1 g/L, ZnSO₄ 1 g/L, MnSO₄ 1 g/L

Fungi : Phosphate Buffer Saline-Tween (PBS-T) (10 mM, pH 7.4)

NaCl	7.6 g/L
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O	2.51 g/L
NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.36 g/L
Tween 80	200 µL/L

Physiological solution (NaCl 0.9%)

NaCl	9 g/L
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Glycerol solution 10%

Glycerol	100 mL/L
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Fungi : Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)

Potato Extract	4 g/L
Dextrose	20 g/L
Agar	15 g/L

Fungi : Malt Extract Agar (MEA)

Glucose	20 g/L
Malt Extract	20 g/L
Peptone	2 g/L
Agar	15 g/L

Fungi : Corn Meal Agar (CMA)

Corn meal	<u>2 g/L</u>
Agar	<u>15 g/L</u>

Fungi : Czapek Dox Agar (CDA)

Sucrose	30 g/L
NaNO ₃	2 g/L
K ₂ HPO ₄	1 g/L
KCl	0.5 g/L
MgSO ₄	0.5 g/L
FeSO ₄	0.01 g/L
Agar	15 g/L

Fungi : Soil Extract Agar (pH 6.8-7.0)

1. Sterilize 400.0 g of air-dried soil (with high content of organic matter) in 1 L tap water for one hour at 121°C.
2. Allow it to sediment for a few hours at room temperature.
3. Centrifuge the supernatant. Add agar 15.0 g/L to the clear supernatant solution thus obtained.
4. Before use, the media were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 20 minutes.

6.5 Isolation of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi

This protocol is based on the procedure described at the INVAM website (<https://invam.ku.edu/trap-cultures>)

1. Collect a mass of soil surrounding the root apparatus, and including the root itself. Depending on the plant considered, 500 g to 1kg of sampled material will be obtained.
2. keep the material in a plastic bag and refrigerated (4°C) until processing (not more than 1 week)
3. Chop the soil-root ball with a sterilized scalpel so that root are chopped into small fragments
4. Mix the chopped material with sterilized sand and vermiculite in the following proportion (50/25/25 volume)
5. Fill 15-cm plastic pots with the mix. Sow seeds of different host plants: ideally 1 monocot, 1 dicot and 1 legume species should be used
6. Let the plant grow for at least 4 months in greenhouse. Fertilize only if needed with a low phosphate Long-Ashton solution (30uM P)

7. At the end of the growing period, pots are disassembled and single AMF propagules are collected under a stereomicroscope and stored at 4°C and used as soon as possible
8. Small pots (200-300 ml vol) are filled with a sterilized substrate (50% sand, 25% vermiculite, 25% perlite) and pre-germinated plantlets are placed in the center, together with single AMF propagules. For this purpose *Medicago truncatula*, Clover (*Trifolium repens*) or *Lotus japonicus* seeds are often used.
9. the pots are watered twice a week, alternatively with tap water and low phosphate Long-Ashton solution (30uM P). Plants are left to grow in greenhouse for 3 months.
10. After 3 months AMF propagules are collected from individual pots and kept separated. A small portion of propagules (1-5) from individual pots is used to extract DNA which is used as template in PCR reactions with SSUmAf1 and LSUmAr3 primers that amplify a portion of the AMF rDNA (Kruger et al., 2009). Amplicons are sent for Sanger sequencing
11. After a dereplication process (see section 4.5.3) based on the results of the Sanger sequencing, the obtained strains are propagated and kept in biobank by multisporal inoculation of host plants.

6.6 Microorganisms_literature_list

During the process of redaction, we have made an extensive bibliography on microorganisms that could have a positive effect or alleviate salt and drought stress. This list would help in the selection of microbial strain for the Synthetic Microbial Community.

6.6.1 Microorganisms reducing/alleviating salt and drought stress in wheat

Wheat growth parameters: physiological traits, antioxidant enzymatic activity, reducing lipid peroxidation, reducing oxidative stress. Shoot and root dry weight, shoot and root length, wheat protein content, chlorophyll a and b, carotenoids, glutathione (GSH), ascorbate, peroxidase, catalase, flavonoids, total soluble protein, stomatal conductance, transpiration rate, and relative water content

Stress responsive genes in wheat: DHN, DREB, L15 and TaABA-8OH, APX1, SAMS1, and HSP17.8, DREB2A and CAT1 (these can be checked in qPCR)

Seed dormancy enforced by salinity can substantially be alleviated and germination promoted by gibberellin, auxin, zeatin and ethephon (Egamberdieva 2009).

Besides the fact that different wheat cultivars can perform differently under salinity (Hetrick, Bockus, and Bloom 1984; Mahoney, Yin, and Hulbert 2017), it has been suggested, that different wheat cultivars might react differently to colonization by these microbial strains (Daei et al. 2009; Cui et al. 2022).

Figure 7: Depiction of how beneficial microbes enhance the performance of wheat under stress.

(A) Shows that in absence of any beneficial host-microbiome interaction, wheat shows compromised growth and overall performance. (B) Shows that after inoculation of wheat by beneficial microbes, its root/shoot biomass and overall performance are enhanced. The figure was created with BioRender.com. (J. Chen et al. 2021)

6.6.2 Results from *in vitro*, greenhouse and field trials

6.6.2.1 Notes on Bacteria and Archaea

Halophilic and halotolerant bacteria. PGP traits: exopolysaccharides (EPS), indole-3-acetic-acid (IAA), phytohormones, regulation of osmotic balance, signal transduction, membrane transport, ACC-deaminase activity (ACCD), hydrogen cyanide production (HCN), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione reductase (GR)

Consortium experiments:

- of ACCD producing bacteria increased wheat salt tolerance: 1. *Enterobacter* sp.12, *Enterobacter* sp. 126 and *Serratia* sp. 73, 2. *Microbacterium* sp. 35, *Pseudomonas* sp. 33, *Serratia* sp. 16 (Barra et al. 2016)
- of PGPR *Bacillus* sp. (KF719179), *Azospirillum brasilense* (KJ194586), *Azospirillum lipoferum* (KJ434039), and *Pseudomonas stutzeri* (KJ685889) increased wheat salt tolerance (Ilyas, Mazhar, et al. 2020).
- of Cyanobacteria, *Nostoc calcicola*, *Nostoc spongiaeformae*, *Nostoc linckia* and *Nostoc muscorum*, EPS, (Arora et al. 2010)
- of mix 1 (*Bacillus thuringiensis* S-26, *Bacillus thuringiensis* D-2, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* S-134, *Bacillus simplex* D-11) and mix 2 (*Moraxella pluranimalium* S-29, *Bacillus simplex* D-1, *Bacillus muralis* D-5, *Pseudomonas stutzeri* S-80) showed significant improvement for tillers and number of spikelets at high water stress (10% FC) (Raheem et al. 2018)

5. mix of *Azospirillum lipoferum*, *Azospirillum brasilense* and *Bacillus* sp. reduced drought effects in wheat (Akhtar et al. 2021)

6. mix of *Bacillus paralicheniformis* (strain A) and *Bacillus subtilis* (strain X) under drought conditions, plant shoot weight significantly increased (J. Li et al. 2023)

Table 4: List of Bacteria and Archaea with salt and drought stress alleviating effects

Genus	Species	Strain	Mechanism	References
Aeromonas	hydrophila	MAS-765	EPS	(Ashraf et al. 2004)
Agrobacterium	fabrum		ACCD	(Danish and Zafar-UI-Hye 2019)
Arthrobacter	sp. D4-14			(Hone et al. 2021)
Azospirillum	brasilense	A07	EPS	(Ilyas, Mumtaz, et al. 2020)
Azospirillum	brasilense	Sp. 245	better water uptake	(Creus, Sueldo, and Barassi 1997)
Azospirillum	brasilense	NO40	upregulation of stress-response genes	(Kasim et al. 2013)
Azospirillum	lipoferum	JA4::ngfp15	-	(Bacilio et al. 2004)
Azospirillum	lipoferum	AZ45	IAA, ipdC gene expression	(Arzanesh et al. 2011, 2009)
Azospirillum	lipoferum	NO40	antioxidative defense	(Agami, Ghramh, and Hasheem 2017)
Azotobacter	chroococcum	LMG 8756	IAA	(Allam et al. 2018)
Azotobacter	vinelandii	DSM576	IAA	(Allam et al. 2018)
Bacillus	altitudinis	WR10	IAA, ACCD	(Z. Yue et al. 2019; Sun et al. 2017)
Bacillus	amyloliquefaciens		ACCD	(Danish and Zafar-UI-Hye 2019)
Bacillus	amyloliquefaciens	5113	upregulation of stress-related genes	(Kasim et al. 2013)
Bacillus	amyloliquefaciens	S-134	phytohormone production	(Raheem et al. 2018)
Bacillus	aryabhatai	PM34	nitrogen fixation, ACCD, potassium, zinc solubilization, IAA, extracellular enzyme activities	(Mehmood et al. 2021)
Bacillus	aryabhatai	EWR29	phosphate solubilization, IAA, siderophore, HCN, ACCD, EPS	(Farahat et al. 2020)
Bacillus	cereus	P5		(Lozo et al. 2023)
Bacillus	cereus	Y5	ACCD	(Rajnish P. Singh and Jha 2016)
Bacillus	cereus	DSM 31T DSM	IAA, HCN	(Desoky et al. 2020)
Bacillus	cereus	MKA4	increase SOD, catalase and GR activity	(Meenakshi et al. 2019)
Bacillus	halodenitrificans	PU62	siderophore, P-solubilization activities	(Ramadoss et al. 2013)
Bacillus	halotolerans	MSR-H4	EPS, IAA production	(El-Akhdar, Elsakhawy, and Abo-Koura 2020)
Bacillus	licheniformis	HSW-16	ACCD, EPS	(Rajnish P. Singh and Jha 2016)
Bacillus	megaterium		ACCD, IAA	(Rashid et al. 2022)
Bacillus	megaterium	NBRC15308	ACCD	(Fathalla and Abd El-Mageed 2020)
Bacillus	methylotrophicus	PM19	EPS, ACCD	(Amna et al. 2019)

Bacillus	muralis	D-5	phytohormone production	(Raheem et al. 2018)
Bacillus	pumilus		IAA, siderophore, P solubilization, ammonia production	(Tiwari et al. 2011)
Bacillus	pumilus	FAB10	production of IAA, siderophore, NH ₃ , HCN and solubilization of phosphate	(Firoz Ahmad Ansari, Ahmad, and Pichtel 2019)
Bacillus	safensis		antioxidant and osmoprotectant production	(Rajnish Prakash Singh and Jha 2016a)
Bacillus	subtilis	B05	EPS	(Ilyas, Mumtaz, et al. 2020)
Bacillus	subtilis	NA2	-	(Gul et al. 2023)
Bacillus	subtilis	Y16	ACCD	(M. Khan et al. 2017)
Bacillus	subtilis	LDR2	enhance photosynthetic efficiency, IAA, ABA, ACCD	(Barnawal et al. 2017)
Bacillus	subtilis	SIR1	ROS reduction	(D. Singh et al. 2023)
Bacillus	subtilis	MKA3	increase SOD, catalase and GR activity	(Meenakshi et al. 2019)
Bacillus	subtilis	SBMP4		(Fathalla and Abd El-Mageed 2020)
Bacillus	subtilis	ssp. inaquosorum	EPS	(Talebi Atouei, Pourbabaee, and Shorafa 2019)
Bacillus	sp. BT3		upregulation of stress responsive genes	(D. Singh, Thapa, et al. 2023)
Bacillus	thuringiensis	AZP2	ACCD, biofilm formation	(Timmusk et al. 2014)
Brucella	pseudogrignonensis		antioxidant and osmoprotectant production	(formerly Ochrobactrum pseudogregnonense) (Singh and Jha 2016)
Chryseobacterium	gleum	sp. SUK	ACCD, IAA, HCN, siderophore	(Bhise, Bhagwat, and Dandge 2017)
Cronobacter	sakazakii	OF115 (KM042090)	ACCD, antioxidant enzymes	(Rajnish Prakash Singh and Jha 2016a)
Curtobacterium	flaccumfaciens	Cf D3-25		(Hone et al. 2021)
Dietzia	natronolimnaea	STR1	enhance photosynthetic efficiency, IAA, expression of stress responsive genes	(Barnawal et al. 2017; Bharti et al. 2016a, 2016b)
Enterobacter	aerogenes	S-10	IAA	(Raheem et al. 2018)
Enterobacter	asburiae		ACCD and regulation of leaf ethylene production	(G. Zhang et al. 2018)
Enterobacter	ludwigii		ROS, upregulation of stress response genes, ACCD and regulation of ethylene production	(Gontia-Mishra et al. 2016; G. Zhang et al. 2018)
Enterobacter	mori		ACCD and regulation of leaf ethylene production	(G. Zhang et al. 2018)
Enterobacter	sp. SBP-6		ACCD activity, phytohormone production, nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization	(Barnawal et al. 2017)
Glutamicibacter	protophormiae	SA3	enhance photosynthetic efficiency, IAA, ABA, ACCD	(formerly Arthrobacter protophormiae) (D. Singh et al. 2023)
Halolamina	pelagica	CDK2	ROS, upregulation of stress response genes	(D. Singh, Kaushik, et al. 2023)
Halobacillus	sp. SL3		siderophore, P-solubilization activities	(Ramadoss et al. 2013)
Klebsiella	variicola	SURYA6	ACCD, IAA, EPS, osmolyte production	(Kusale et al. 2021)

Klebsiella	sp. HA9		upregulation of stress responsive genes	(D. Singh, Thapa, et al. 2023)
Kocuria	rhizophila	14ASP (KF875448)	ACCD, antioxidant enzymes	(Rajnish Prakash Singh and Jha 2016b)
Lelliottia	amnigena	MSR-M49	EPS, IAA production	(Khan et al. 2022)
Marinobacter	lipolyticus	SM19	EPS	(Talebi Atouei, Pourbabae, and Shorafa 2019)
Nocardioides	sp. NIMMe6		IAA and salicylic acid production	(Singh and Jha 2016b)
Pantoea	agglomerans	Pa	IAA, ACCD, P solubilization	(Cherif-Silini et al. 2019)
Pantoea	alhagi	LYR-11ZT		(4. Chen et al. 2021)
Paenarthrobacter	nitroguajacolicus		up-regulation of various genes	(formerly Arthrobacter nitroguajacolicus) (Safdarian et al. 2019)
Paraburkholderia	phytofirmans	PsJN	ACCD, siderophores, phytohormone production	(formerly Burkholderia phytofirmans) (Naveed et al. 2014)
Pseudomonas	aeruginosa	N39	ACCD	(Zahir et al. 2009)
Pseudomonas	aeruginosa	DSM 50071T	IAA, HCN	(Desoky et al. 2020)
Pseudomonas	azotoformans	FAP5	production of EPS, IAA, solubilized tricalcium phosphate and exhibited ACCD	(F. A. Ansari, Jabeen, and Ahmad 2021)
Pseudomonas	chlororaphis	30-84	phenazine production	(Mahmoudi et al. 2019)
Pseudomonas	extremorientalis	TSAU6	IAA production	(Egamberdieva 2009)
Pseudomonas	extremorientalis	TSAU20	IAA production	(Egamberdieva 2009)
Pseudomonas	fluorescens		ACCD	(Nadeem, Zahir, and Naveed 2010)
Pseudomonas	fluorescens	DPB15	ACCD, SOD, CAT, GPX and APX	(Chandra, Srivastava, and Sharma 2018)
Pseudomonas	fluorescens	NBRC14160	ACCD, nitrogen fixation	(Fathalla and Abd El-Mageed 2020)
Pseudomonas	libanensis	EU-LWNA-33	P-solubilization	(Kour et al. 2020)
Pseudomonas	moraviensis		ACCD	(Yaseen et al. 2020)
Pseudomonas	palleroniana	DPB16	ACCD, SOD, CAT, GPX and APX	(Chandra, Srivastava, and Sharma 2018)
Pseudomonas	putida		ACCD	(Nadeem, Zahir, and Naveed 2010; Lozo et al. 2023)
Pseudomonas	putida	N21	ACCD	(Rajnish Prakash Singh and Jha 2016b)
Rhizobium	leguminosarum	LBM1220	gene regulation	(Barquero et al. 2022)
Rhizobium	leguminosarum	LET4910	gene regulation	(Barquero et al. 2022)
Psychrobacillus	insolitus	MAS17	EPS	(formerly Bacillus insolitus)(Ashraf et al. 2004)
Serratia	proteomaculans	M35	ACCD	(Li et al. 2020)
Serratia	sp. SL-12		IAA, phosphate solubilization, ACCD	(Rajnish Prakash Singh and Jha 2016b)
Serratia	marcescens	DSM 12485	IAA, HCN	(Desoky et al. 2020)
Streptomyces	coelicolor	DE07		(Yandigeri et al. 2012)
Streptomyces	olivaceus	DE10	IAA	(Yandigeri et al. 2012)
Streptomyces	geysiriensis	DE27		(Yandigeri et al. 2012)
Streptomyces	pactum	Act12	upregulation of resistance-related genes	(H. Li et al. 2020)

Table 5: Taxonomy of prokaryotic species from literature

Species	Phylum	Class	Order	Family
<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i>	Pseudomonadota (Proteobacteria)	Gammaproteobacteria	Aeromonadales	Aeromonadaceae
<i>Agrobacterium fabrum</i>	Pseudomonadota	Alphaproteobacteria	Hyphomicrobiales	Rhizobiaceae
<i>Arthrobacter sp. D4-14</i>	Actinomycetota (Actinobacteria)	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae
<i>Azospirillum brasilense</i>	Pseudomonadota	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodospirillales	Rhodospirillaceae
<i>Azospirillum lipoferum</i>	Pseudomonadota	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhodospirillales	Rhodospirillaceae
<i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Azotobacter vinelandii</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Bacillus altitudinis</i>	Bacillota (Firmicutes)	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus aryabhatai</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus halodenitrificans</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus halotolerans</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus methylophilus</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus muralis</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus sp. BT3</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Brucella pseudogrignonensis</i>	Pseudomonadota	Alphaproteobacteria	Rhizobiales	Brucellaceae
<i>Chryseobacterium gleum</i>	Bacteroidetes	Flavobacteriia	Flavobacteriales	Flavobacteriaceae
<i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Cronobacteraceae
<i>Curtobacterium flaccumfaciens</i>	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae
<i>Dietzia natronolimnaea</i>	Actinobacteria	Actinobacteria	Corynebacteriales	Dietziaceae
<i>Enterobacter</i>	asburiae	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae

<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Enterobacter ludwigii</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Enterobacter</i> sp. SBP-6	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Glutamicibacter protophormiae</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae
<i>Halolamina pelagica</i>	Euryarcheota	Halobacteria	Haloferacales	Halorubraceae
<i>Halobacillus</i> sp. SL3	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Klebsiella variicola</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp. HA9	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Kocuria rhizophila</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Microbacteriaceae
<i>Lelliottia amnigena</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Enterobacteriaceae
<i>Marinobacter lipolyticus</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Marinobacteraceae
<i>Nocardioides</i> sp. NIMMe6	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Propionibacteriales	Nocardioideaceae
<i>Paenarthrobacter nitroguajacolicus</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Micrococcales	Micrococcaceae
<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Erwiniaceae
<i>Pantoea alhagi</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Erwiniaceae
<i>Paraburkholderia phytofirmans</i>	Pseudomonadota	Betaproteobacteria	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas azotoformans</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas chlororaphis</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas extremorientalis</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas libanensis</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas moraviensis</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas palleroniana</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Pseudomonadales	Pseudomonadaceae
<i>Psychrobacillus insolitus</i>	Bacillota	Bacilli	Bacillales	Bacillaceae
<i>Serratia proteomaculans</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Yersiniaceae
<i>Serratia</i> sp. SL-12	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Yersiniaceae
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Pseudomonadota	Gammaproteobacteria	Enterobacterales	Yersiniaceae

<i>Streptomyces coelicolor</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Streptomycetales	Streptomycetaceae
<i>Streptomyces olivaceus</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Streptomycetales	Streptomycetaceae
<i>Streptomyces geysiriensis</i>	Actinomycetota	Actinobacteria	Streptomycetales	Streptomycetaceae

6.6.2.2 Notes on Fungi

Consortium experiments:

1. mix of *Rhizophagus irregularis*, *Funneliformis mosseae* lowered salt stress level (Fileccia et al. 2017)
2. mix of *Rhizophagus intraradices*, *Funneliformis mosseae*, *Funneliformis geosporum* alleviated drought stress (Mathur, Tomar, and Jajoo 2019)

Plenty of the studies were on seed biopriming with fungal strains.

Table 6: List of Fungi with salt or drought stress alleviating effects

Genus	Species	Strain	Mechanism	References
Alternaria	alternata			(X. Li et al. 2022)
Alternaria	alternata	LQ1230	IAA	(Qiang et al. 2019)
Aspergillus	fumigatus	ON307213	catalase, SOD	(George et al. 2024)
Aspergillus	terreus	BTK-1	primary and secondary metabolism modulation	(M. I. Khan et al. 2022)
Chaetomium	globosum			(Zhang, Gan, and Xu 2016, 2019)
Funneliformis	mosseae		(formerly <i>Glomus mosseae</i>)	(Daei et al. 2009)
Glomus	etunicatum		-	(S. Zhang, Gan, and Xu 2016, 2019)
Microsphaeropsis	arundinis			(N et al. 2022)
Paraphoma	pye			(X. Li et al. 2022)
Paraphoma	radicina			(X. Li et al. 2022)
Phanerochaete	chrysosporium		increasing the activity of antioxidant enzymes; superoxide dismutase, catalase, and ascorbate peroxidase	(Dief et al. 2021)
Rhizophagus	irregularis		(formerly <i>Glomus intraradices</i>)	(Zhu et al. 2016) (Daei et al. 2009; Moucheshi, Heidari, and Assad 2012; Ratajczak et al. 2020)
Trichoderma	harzianum		-	(Rawat et al. 2011)
Trichoderma	longibrachiatum	T6	increased antioxidative systems, IAA, ACCD	(S. Zhang, Gan, and Xu 2016, 2019)
Trichoderma	reesei	QM6a	IAA	(Ikram et al. 2019)

Table 7: Taxonomy of fungal species from literature

	Fungal Species	Phylum	Class	Order	Family
1	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Ascomycota	Dothideomycetes	Pleosporales	Pleosporaceae
2	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Ascomycota	Eurotiomycetes	Eurotiales	Aspergillaceae
3	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	Ascomycota	Eurotiomycetes	Eurotiales	Aspergillaceae
4	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Sordariales	Chaetomiaceae
5	<i>Funneliformis mosseae</i>	Glomeromycota	Glomeromycetes	Glomerales	Glomeraceae
6	<i>Glomus etunicatum</i>	Glomeromycota	Glomeromycetes	Glomerales	Glomeraceae
7	<i>Microsphaeropsis arundinis</i>	Ascomycota	Dothideomycetes	Pleosporales	Botryosphaeriaceae
8	<i>Paraphoma pye</i>	Ascomycota	Dothideomycetes	Pleosporales	Davidiellaceae
9	<i>Paraphoma radicina</i>	Ascomycota	Dothideomycetes	Pleosporales	Davidiellaceae
10	<i>Phanerochaete chrysosporium</i>	Basidiomycota	Agaricomycetes	Polyporales	Phanerochaetaceae
11	<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i>	Glomeromycota	Glomeromycetes	Glomerales	Glomeraceae
12	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Hypocreales	Hypocreaceae
13	<i>Trichoderma longibrachiatum</i>	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Hypocreales	Hypocreaceae
14	<i>Trichoderma reesei</i>	Ascomycota	Sordariomycetes	Hypocreales	Hypocreaceae

6.6.3 Microbiome changes in salinity and drought stress experiments

Phenazine (antibiotic phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA)) producing bacteria, such as *Pseudomonas* spp. are more abundant in the rhizosphere of wheat grown under dry conditions (D. V. Mavrodi et al. 2018; O. V. Mavrodi et al. 2012). Furthermore, roots of dryland wheat harbor diverse communities dominated by Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Actinobacteria, and Acidobacteria (D. V. Mavrodi et al. 2018). Increase in Actinobacteria, Microbacteriaceae in wheat subjected to drought stress was observed (Hone et al. 2021; Naylor et al. 2017). In saline-alkali soil, *Flavobacterium*, *Aeromonas*, *Acidovorax*, *Confluentibacter*, and *Rhodobacter* were significantly enriched in wheat introgression line JN177 roots, while *Ralstonia*, *Skermanella*, *Rhodococcus*, *Curtobacterium*, *Methylotenera*, *Blastococcus*, *Pseudonocardia*, et4. were significantly enriched in wheat SR4 roots and these greatly altered Na⁺ and K⁺ contents in the roots and shoots of JN177 and SR4 (Cui et al. 2022) (Figure 2).

Figure 8: The conceptual model of the mechanism by which wheat root microbiome affecting host resistance to salt-alkali stress. Salt-alkali stress activates genes that are specifically expressed in SR4 roots, which changes root microenvironment and recruits beneficial microorganisms, and eventually improves the resistance of SR4 to salt-alkali stress (Cui et al. 2022).

The rhizosphere microbiome of wheat seedling under salt treatment consisted at phylum level of Proteobacteria (36.8–56.2%), Firmicutes (1.3–30.0%), Actinobacteria (7.0–20.3%), Verrucomicrobia (1.9–27.6%), Bacteroidetes (2.7–14.7%), Gemmatimonadetes (0.7–12.7%), Chloroflexi (0.4–4.8%), Planctomycetes (1.1–3.5%), Acidobacteria (0.0–3.9%), and Thaumarchaeota (0.1–3.8%); and five most abundant classes in the rhizosphere were Alphaproteobacteria (19.1 to 43.8%), Gammaproteobacteria (4.1 to 25.7%), Bacilli (1.2 to 26.7%), Verrucomicrobiae (0.2 to 25.2%), and Actinobacteria (4.5 to 16.3%) (no data on non-salt-treated wheat rhizosphere, the focus of the study was different) (Szoboszlay et al. 2019). Rhizosphere of wheat responds with microbial changes according to another experiment, the drought-enriched OTUs included the bacterial genera *Massilia* and *Pedobacter* and the fungal genera *Mortierella* and *Gibberella*. As for drought-depleted OTUs, the bacterial genera *Ramlibacter* and *Knoellia* and the fungal genera *Epicoccum* and *Fusicolla* were confirmed using enrichment analyses (H. Yue et al. 2024). Furthermore, they also discovered, that among the tested wheat varieties the drought-resistant variety possessed more complex rhizosphere microbial interkingdom interaction networks. In these networks bacterial and fungal OTUs, including *Bacillus*, *Streptomyces*, and *Mortierella*, could act as potential “keystone taxa” in heightening the drought resistant for drought-resistant variety (H. Yue et al. 2024). Another study showed that relative abundances of wheat rhizosphere Bacteroidetes, Gemmatimonadetes, Patescibacteria and Proteobacteria decreased, while Acidobacteria, Chloroflexi and Firmicutes for ‘Dichter’ wheat variety, and Rokubacteria and Thaumarchaeota for ‘RGT-Reform’ variety were increased under drought (Breitkreuz et al. 2021). Moreover, Actinobacteria diversity increased in the Chernozem soil type, which increased by trend under drought in the rhizospheres of both wheat cultivars in the aforementioned experiment. Under drought stress, the biodiversity in the soil decreased significantly in samples from six regions in Belgium, but increased in the root endosphere community, where specific soil parameters seemingly determine the enrichment of bacterial groups (Si et al. 2021). They identified a cluster of drought-enriched bacteria that significantly correlated with soil compositions,

Actinobacteria were enriched across all soil types, but Fibrobacteres were depleted by drought. Both in wheat endosphere and soil samples, Actinobacteria, Chloroflexi, Acidobacteria, and Gemmatimonadetes were drought enriched, but Fibrobacteres generally drought depleted; *Streptomyces* presented the highest number of matching ASVs enriched under drought stress (Si et al. 2021). Another soil experiment found Actinobacteria abundances significantly higher across all plant compartments under low SWC, while abundance of Firmicutes associated with the root and leaf was significantly higher; Acidobacteria associated with the rhizosphere and root had significantly lower relative abundances in drought samples; under low SWC (5–8% SWHC) (Azarbad et al. 2020). Interestingly, the rhizosphere of plants growing in the soil with history of water stress harboured significantly more Actinobacteria and less Ascomycota as compared with the rhizosphere of plants growing in the soil with no water stress history and higher abundance of Ascomycota in drought tolerant wheat genotypes (AC Barrie and Strongfield (Azarbad et al. 2020). In a colonization experiment of various microbe mixes *Bacillus paralicheniformis* and *Bacillus subtilis*, emerged as the keystone taxa in sandy soil and showed high abundance as well (J. Li et al. 2023) (in my opinion these microbiome results are a bit statistically questionable though, the high abundance of this isolate might skew the overall microbial community composition, leading to an apparent dominance of this isolate in the OTU analysis and the co-occurrence network). There was a study where the composition and abundance of the wheat root-associated fungi were not found to be significantly influenced by drought stress, however, *Trichoderma longibrachiatum* and *T. velutinum* were observed only in the plants grown under drought stress (Salamon et al. 2020). The mycobiome of drought-stressed wheat seeds experienced a depletion of Ascomycota with an increased occurrence of phytopathogens (Vujanovic, Islam, and Daida 2019).

6.6.4 References

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